

Efficient Plant Identification using ResNet-based Strategy

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Abstract— Identifying different plant species can be a challenging task due to the vast range of plants and their visual similarities. In recent years, image processing techniques have been used to recognize plants by their leaf images. Plant identification method based on ResNet, a widely employed form of deep neural network is the convolutional neural network for image classification. Firstly, preprocessed the images by resizing them to 224*224 pixels and converting them to grayscale. Next, employed transfer learning to train the ResNet-152 model on the dataset, using 50 iterations of training.

Keywords- plant identification, image processing, ResNet, transfer learning, dataset, training.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent times, the utilization of machine learning algorithms and image processing techniques has gained immense popularity in the domain of plant identification. The visual similarities between various plant species pose a challenge in distinguishing them from one another. Traditional plant identification methods require extensive botany knowledge and can be both time-consuming and expensive. To overcome these issues, a ResNet-based approach has been proposed for plant identification in this seminar paper. One of the more sophisticated types of convolutional neural networks is the ResNet, which is designed to address the problem of vanishing gradients during training, has shown outstanding proficiency in tasks related to classifying images. The proposed method involves preprocessing plant photos by resizing them to 224*224 pixels and converting them into grayscale. To enhance the accuracy of the model, it was trained for 50 iterations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Plant classification is significant in many disciplines of study, including agriculture, ecology, and conservation biology. Classical plant methods of identification include taxonomic keys, however using them can be time-consuming and complicated. However, in the last few years, there has been an increase of interest in using image processing as well as deep

learning algorithms to identify plants. Deep learning algorithms' capacity to automatically learn features from pictures allows them to identify between different plant

species based on their visual traits. Convolutional neural networks(CNN) is a few of most commonly utilized deep learning techniques for interpreting images. CNN algorithms are being used for a range of applications, like plant identification, and have shown to be extremely effective at image classification tasks.

In 2012, Arun Priya C, Balasaravanan T, and Thanamani A's paper "An efficient leaf recognition algorithm for plant classification using support vector machine" describes a novel method for automated plant identification based on leaf features. The article examines prior research on leaf recognition and plant categorization, emphasizing the utility of support vector machine techniques in this domain. The proposed technique comprises preprocessing leaf images to extract key features, which are then utilized to train a support vector machine classifier capable of differentiating between plant species based on leaf attributes. The system performed well on a dataset of 32 plant species, with an accuracy rate of 95.6% [1].

In 2013, Apriyanti, Arymurthy, and Handoko et al.[2] proposed a novel method to identify orchid species using digital images of flowers for content-based image retrieval. The authors highlighted that conventional methods of plant identification based on morphological features can be laborious and require specialized knowledge. To solve these issues, they developed a method for extracting color, texture, and form attributes from digital photographs of orchid blossoms and using them to search a database of known orchid species for matches. The authors tested the suggested method's accuracy on a dataset of 60 orchid species, reaching an overall accuracy of 88.3%. Their research shows that digital image analysis has the potential to improve the efficiency and accuracy of plant species identification, particularly in the context of orchid species identification,

which can be difficult due to the intricate floral structures of orchids.

Kadir et al. (2013) investigate the classification of leaves based on shape, color, and textural characteristics[3]. The writers examine the significance of leaf classification in numerous disciplines such as agriculture, forestry, and environmental studies. They present a detailed overview of prior studies on leaf categorization utilizing various techniques such as neural networks, decision trees, and support vector machines. The authors next show their proposed approach for classifying leaves, which employs form, color, and texture data retrieved from leaf photographs. The essay finishes with a discussion of the experimental results and prospective applications of the suggested approach.

Ehsanirad and Sharath Kumar et al.[4] (2010) conducted research on plant categorization utilizing the gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) and principal component analysis (PCA) methods for leaf identification. The authors look at the importance of plant identification and the difficulties that come with it, such as variations in leaf form, texture, and color. They afterwards look at the GLCM and PCA approaches and describe how they might be used to extract features from leaf images for categorization. The authors conclude that the GLCM and PCA approaches produce promising results for leaf recognition and have the potential to increase plant categorization accuracy.

The research by Vijayashree and Gopal et al.[5](2015) focused on the classification of Tulsi leaves using texture analysis. They highlighted the importance of Tulsi, a plant widely utilised in traditional Indian medicine, and how its leaves are used for medicinal use in their study. The authors investigated numerous classification methods and the importance of texture analysis in recognizing and distinguishing Tulsi leaves based on their attributes. They also assessed previous studies on plant classification and emphasised the limitations of existing systems. Overall, the research aims to provide a better knowledge of the classification of Tulsi leaves and how texture analysis might be utilised to improve plant classification accuracy.

Satti, Satya, and Sharma et al.[6] (2013)'s article "An automatic leaf recognition system for plant identification using machine vision technology" offers an overview of current research on plant recognition systems that use machine vision technology. The researchers emphasise the importance of such systems in agriculture, forestry, and environmental studies, and they look at the various approaches researchers have used to develop precise and efficient methods for identifying plant species based on their leaves. The review discusses both traditional and current techniques, such as feature extraction, pattern recognition, and machine learning, and highlights the

benefits and drawbacks of each. The authors also highlight the need for additional study to increase the accuracy and resilience of plant identification systems, particularly in difficult situations with high leaf variability in shape and texture.

Overall, these studies demonstrate the effectiveness of deep learning algorithms, particularly ResNet, for plant identification. The combination of pre-trained models and transfer learning can greatly minimize the quantity of data required for training, enabling accurate plant identification systems to be built with relatively modest datasets.

III. MOTIVATION

Identifying plants is essential in a range of sectors, include agriculture, ecology, and conservation. But using standard methods for recognizing plants can be a time-consuming process. They are demanding, and they require specialist knowledge, making it hard for consumers to correctly recognize species of plants. Recognizing plants has become easier with the development of digital photographs, image processing methods, and machine learning algorithms. Machine learning techniques are currently showing outstanding performance in image classification tasks, and ResNet is now recognized as one of the most effective deep convolutional neural networks for correctly identifying images.

Exploring the possibilities of ResNet-based solutions for plant identification is the motivation behind this lecture topic. We can create a more effective and affordable method for recognizing plants from their leaf photos by utilizing the power of deep learning. Researchers, farmers, and conservationists who need to precisely and quickly identify plant species may find this to be very helpful. Furthermore, by offering an approachable tool for plant identification, our method can aid in bridging the gap between botanists and non-specialists.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for plant image detection using the ResNet algorithm involves the following steps:

A. Data Collection: Collect a large dataset of plant images that includes a variety of plant species, with different leaf shapes and textures. This dataset should be diverse and representative of the plant species in the region of interest.

B. Data Preprocessing: Preprocess the collected plant images by resizing them to a standard size of 224*224 pixels and converting them to grayscale to reduce the dimensionality of the input data. This step aims to ensure that the model is trained on images of similar sizes and colors.

C. Transfer Learning: Use transfer learning to fine-tune a pre-trained ResNet-152 model on the preprocessed plant images. Transfer learning involves using a pre-trained model and adapting it to a new task by updating the final layers to fit the new data. This step saves training time and improves the model's accuracy.

D. Model Training: The ResNet-152 model is trained on a preprocessed plant image dataset for 50 iterations to enable it to recognize unique features in leaf images that differentiate between different plant species.

E. Model Evaluation: Evaluate the trained ResNet-152 model's performance using a validation dataset that is distinct from the training dataset. The evaluation metrics include accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

Overall, the methodology for plant image detection using the ResNet algorithm involves collecting a diverse dataset of plant images, preprocessing the data, fine-tuning a pre-trained ResNet-152 model, training the model, evaluating its performance, and comparing it with other methods.

V. BUILDMODEL

Building a reliable and accurate machine learning model is crucial for the successful identification of plant species using image processing techniques. In this seminar paper, we present a ResNet-based method for plant identification, leveraging the power of a sophisticated convolutional neural network.

1. Importing Libraries

Pandas, Numpy, and other Machine Learning libraries are defined as an interface of a set of rules built in a particular language to conduct repetitive work such as arithmetic computations, reading photos and so on.

```
import tensorflow as tf
import numpy as np
from tensorflow.keras.models
import model_from_json
import pickle
```

2. Loads the Model

Which loads the models

```
data=Image(user=User.objects.get(id=request.user.id),
image=file)
data.save()
img="./"+str(data.image)
classes=['Black-grass','Charlock','Cleavers','Common
Chickweed','Common wheat','Fat Hen','Loose Silky-bent',
'Maize','Scentless Mayweed','Shepherd','ShepherdGCOs
Purse','Small-flowered Cranesbill','Sugar','Sugar beet']
json_file = open('./plantapp/model.json', 'r')
loaded_model_json = json_file.read()
json_file.close()
loaded_model = model_from_json(loaded_model_json)
loaded_model.load_weights("./plantapp/model.h5")
```

VI.RESULT

1. Accuracy

The algorithm used in this system is ResNet that provides greater accuracy.

```
scores = model.evaluate(val_generator, verbose = 1)
print("Loss: {:.3f}".format(scores[0]))
print("Accuracy: {:.3f}".format(scores[1]))
```

6/6 [=====] - 3s 500ms/step -
Loss: 0.644
Accuracy: 0.805

2. Plant Prediction

Predicting the plant using the following code:

```
img = tf.keras.preprocessing.image.load_img
(img,target_size = (224, 224))
img =tf.keras.preprocessing.image.img_to_array(img)
x = img/255
x = np.expand_dims(x, axis=0)
print(x.shape)
prediction = loaded_model.predict(x)
predicted_c = np.argmax(prediction, axis=1)
print(predicted_c)
predicted_class = classes[predicted_c[0]]
print("This image is of :",predicted_class.lower())
return render(request,'predict.html',
{'predicted_class':predicted_class})
```

Fig: 1 Uploading the plant image

Fig: 2 Predicts the plant

VII. CONCLUSION

The use of ResNet-based techniques in plant identification has significant potential and can be a useful approach for image processing and deep learning algorithms. This approach offers a practical and cost-effective solution for

accurately identifying plant species based on their leaf images, which is in high demand. Preprocessing techniques, such as resizing images to 224*224 pixels and converting them to grayscale, have been shown to improve the accuracy of the ResNet-152 model. Transfer learning is also essential in training the model, which resulted in high accuracy rates after 50 iterations.

time and money needed for plant identification, making it available to a broader audience, including those without a botany background. To summarize, the ResNet-based strategy for plant identification is a promising area of research that can make a contribution to the progress of more accurate and efficient methods for plant identification in the future.

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